

MOTIVATION IS ONE OF THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTORS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: Motivation is one of the major factors which influence learning. Motivation is a pulling force which “provides the primary impetus to initiate learning the L2 and later the driving force to sustain the long and often tedious learning process”. While researchers and scholars differ regarding the definitions of term, they seem to agree “that motivation is responsible for determining human behavior by energizing it and giving it direction”. Motivation is a psychological term which is considered, in language learning processes, to be the desire, necessity, or wish to learn or acquire something. This article is discussed the importance of motivation in language learning.

Key words: motivation, methods of teaching language, types of motivating

Students with a good attitude towards English are more likely to work hard and keep going when learning gets challenging. Our exams are designed to motivate students by building their confidence step by step. We aim to bring learning to life – covering topics that students are familiar with and developing the skills they need to make friends, study and work in English.

There are two main types of motivation.

- Learning English for a particular purpose – for example to get a job, get into university, to travel.
- Learning English because you enjoy learning, having fun and making progress. This tends to be the most effective form of motivation.¹

Students are also more motivated when they have a positive impression of English-speaking people and cultures. If they like the music, films or sports, they are more likely to want to learn the language.

Essentially, it’s the same. Learners of all ages achieve more when they are intrinsically motivated. In other words, when the learning experience is fun, interesting and meaningful.

Students will want to learn if they have extrinsic motivation, such as getting a reward for good results, or needing English for university studies. But as Steve Jobs said: ‘The only way to do great work is to love what you do.’

Research shows that parents' attitudes towards education have a significant impact on their students's attitudes towards learning. If you are enthusiastic about learning, it's more likely that your students will be too.

Just like any other skill, motivation can be encouraged and improved. Students are most motivated when:

- They feel that a learning activity is interesting and meaningful.
- Give your students lots of opportunities to explore their interests and favourite play activities in English. Any language 'work' you do at home that is fun, varied, attention-grabbing or creative will help your students prepare for their tests and develop their English language skills in a natural, stress-free way.
- They believe that the learning activity can be successfully completed.
- It's important to have learning activities at the right level. If an activity is far too easy or too difficult, it can be uninspiring and demoralising.
- Students have different preferences for how they take in information. Some like to listen to explanations and discuss, some like to look at diagrams and pictures, some like to actively experiment and create. Make a note of what works best – success builds motivation.
- They have some control over how to do the activity.
- It can be really motivating to have some choices. It usually encourages students to work harder and produce more creative work. It also helps them learn to take control of their own learning and be responsible for their decisions.
- They will get approval from someone they care about.
- Like everyone, students want to be 'good' at things and want their parents to be proud of them. Praise them to create a sense of success and encourage them when they take 'risks'. Help them turn mistakes into opportunities for learning.

You could try saving a piece of work or videoing an activity your students has enjoyed doing. Put a date in the calendar to do the activity again. Then compare the two pieces of work and focus on your students' achievements. This is a clear way to show your students how they are improving in their studies.

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